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Peculiarities of accounting and analytical support of discontinued operations of a commercial organization

KEYWORDS

discontinued operations,
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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The study of partial or complete businesses liquidation is essential for understanding market dynamics, risk management, and developing strategies for the sustainable development of enterprises in uncertain conditions.

The article aims to study the peculiarities of accounting for discontinued operations of the enterprise.

Materials and Methods. Scientific research in accounting, financial analysis and management, as well as literature on accounting and financial management, accounting standards, and legislative acts related to the liquidation and termination of enterprises, were analyzed.

Results of the study. To create a valuation liability for discontinued operations, it is necessary not only to develop a detailed plan for “going out of business” but also to make all interested parties (dismissed employees, labor unions, counterparties, etc.) aware of it. Information on discontinued operations should be reflected in the explanatory notes to the balance sheet and the statement of financial results, and in the case of a bankrupt company, in our opinion, in the report of the bankruptcy trustee.

Conclusion. Creating and implementing unified international accounting standards for discontinued operations can ensure consistency and transparency in financial reporting, allowing a more accurate reflection of enterprises' financial situations.

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INTRODUCTION

In times of economic instability, crises, or changes in the market environment, companies may need to scale down their operations or close down completely. This may be due to reduced demand, increased competition, or changes in legislation. Business liquidation affects employees, customers, and partners, which makes it essential to analyze the socio-economic impacts and possible measures to mitigate the adverse effects.

Thus, the study of partial or complete business liquidation is essential for understanding market dynamics, managing risk, and developing strategies for sustainable enterprise development under uncertainty.

Literature Review

A. Srivastava finds that timely recognition of losses increases the probability of timely closure of unprofitable projects. By announcing the late termination of such projects, managers show their inability to select suitable projects and/or contain losses when projects become unprofitable. The authors also argue that business organizations that announce significant termination losses reduce capital expenditures and improve loss recognition timeliness in subsequent years. In other words, timely loss reporting creates economic benefits [1]. Although, as T. Bates writes, numerous owners of closed firms often viewed their business as 'successful' at the time of the decision to cease operations [2].

For example, in the United States, the Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB) requires separate accounting for discontinued operations in the income statement to provide more accurate information about companies' future earnings for financial statement users. However, discontinued operations can complicate earnings forecasting because some continuing revenues are eliminated, the future impact on continuing operations may not be clear, and there are incentives for opportunistic reporting [3].

B. Guragai et al. study the relationship between discontinued operations and future improvement in financial performance (SFAS 144). According to the authors, companies experience an improvement in economic performance after reporting discontinued operations: the performance improvement is more significant for companies that discontinue unprofitable operations than those that discontinue profitable operations [4].

According to A. Barua et al., numerous companies transfer operating expenses to decrease income from discontinued operations to increase the primary income [5].

It should be clarified that in Russia, in RAS accounting, intangible assets are regulated by the Federal Law dated 06.12.11 № 402-FZ 'On Accounting' and the Accounting Regulation dated 27.12.2007 № 153n 14/2007 'Accounting for Intangible Assets' (Accounting standards

14/2007). On the US GAAP side, intangible assets are governed by SFAS No. 142 and SFAS No. 144, 'Accounting for the Impairment or Disposal of Long-Lived Assets', and other documents.

A. Curtis finds that the broader scope of rules under SFAS 144 results in more robust continuing income among firms reporting discontinued operations [6].

S. E. Kaplan et al. show that preliminary taxable income and operating expenses are significantly more relevant when increasing revenue from discontinued operations. This supports their economic explanation for why firms do not shift operating expenses into increasing the income from discontinued operations [7].

Audit, as an independent accounting review, helps ensure transparency in the liquidation process and protect the interests of all stakeholders. Depending on the laws of the country and the specific circumstances, an audit may be mandatory when a company is liquidated. In most cases, an audit is required to confirm that the financial statements are correct and that all obligations to creditors and tax authorities have been met.

However, according to A. Gaeremynck, it is necessary to understand the differences between companies, i.e., when financial difficulties are apparent, as in the case of a company on the verge of bankruptcy, and when financial problems are not so obvious, as in the case of firms that voluntarily decide to liquidate. In these cases, not all auditors can show competence and independence [8; 9].

Thus, the scientific problem of accounting for a company's discontinued operations is the need for a clear definition and the correct classification of assets and liabilities associated with these activities. The scientific problem also involves developing and justifying the most effective accounting methods. Determining how information about discontinued operations should be reported is essential to ensure transparency and reliability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To study the problem of accounting for discontinued operations of the company, scientific research in the field of accounting, financial analysis, and management published in peer-reviewed journals: "The Accounting Review," "Review of Accounting and Finance," "Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting," "Accounting and Business Research" and numerous others were used. The literature on accounting, financial management, and legal aspects of business liquidation, accounting standards (e.g., IFRS, RAS), and legislative acts related to liquidation and termination of businesses were also used.

Research methods: analysis of existing studies and publications on the topic; comparative analysis of different approaches to accounting for discontinued operations in other countries or industries.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

The inability to operate in the previous mode due to changes in market conditions, pandemic, imposition of legal restrictions, and international sanctions has led to the suspension or termination of numerous companies. Depending on the owners' plans, availability, and size of liabilities, there are several alternatives for the shutdown: resumption of operations is planned (yes/no); there are outstanding liabilities (yes/no); available assets are sufficient to repay liabilities (yes/no). As a rule, all of them imply an algorithm of sequential actions associated with additional expenses of the organization (wages to employees for the period of forced downtime or severance pay; expenses for conservation and de-conservation of equipment; remuneration to the bankruptcy trustee, expenses for organizing and conducting electronic trading and other bankruptcy procedures; losses due to urgent sale of assets, etc.).

Moreover, the business entity, using these or those assets to obtain economic benefits, is responsible for possible damage to the environment or other persons. Some of the associated costs are included in the current expenses in the form of mineral extraction tax, environmental fees, maintenance of treatment facilities, etc. Some arise at the stage of "going out of business." However, it is necessary to remember them and consider them when justifying the choice of company type of activity. The expenses considered in forming prospecting assets (related to environmental protection, dismantling and liquidating equipment and other fixed assets, land reclamation, etc.) are mandatory.

In this regard, forming accounting and analytical support for discontinued operations is particularly important.

In the specialized literature, discontinued operations (Discontinued operations) are defined as "activities that are expected or planned to be discontinued" [10]. For Russian accounting, a necessary condition is the ability to directly identify operationally or functionally assets, liabilities, income, and expenses attributable to discontinued operations. This is possible if they are sold, repaid, or otherwise disposed of due to the discontinued operations. By the latest amendments to RAS 16/02 "Information on Discontinued Operations" [11], its scope also includes information on the discontinued use of certain assets if such assets are considered to be long-term assets for sale. This category in our study is of interest regarding expenses from preparing fixed assets for disposal. Other aspects of accounting for long-term assets are beyond the scope of this article.

Currently, RAS 16/02 'Information on Discontinued Operations' considers discontinued operations on the following grounds:

We believe a separate item is to be named termination of the enterprise's activity due to its bankruptcy. On the one hand, the sale of the debtor's property fits into the scheme of a planned

sale of fixed assets or a property complex. On the other hand, when implementing bankruptcy procedures, the legal side prevails over the organizational side and largely determines the amount and composition of expenses.

Figure 1 Methods of termination of activity

By paragraph 7 of Accounting standards 16/02, "Information on discontinued operations," "activities are recognized as discontinued if the authorized body of the organization of the decision to terminate the part of the organization's activities and the development of a unified program of termination on the date of the earliest of the following events: the organization's conclusion of contracts for the sale and purchase of assets, without which the activities allocated as discontinued, practically unfeasible; communication of information about the decision to suspend activities to legal entities and individuals, as well as the decision to terminate the activities of the organization. [Ibid.]

Accordingly, the object of reflection in accounting and reporting these "plans" will become in the reporting period of fulfillment of at least one of these conditions. The primary purpose of Accounting standards 16/02, "Information on discontinued operations," is to allocate relevant information in the organization's accounting statements. That is, during the year, it is, by and large, insignificant. However, its presence and disclosure in annual reports are essential due to the need to confirm or refute the assumption of continuity of the company's activities.

If information on forthcoming discontinued operations arises in bankruptcy proceedings, it should, in our opinion, be disclosed as of the date of introduction of the relevant procedure.

When discontinuing operations, the company incurs income and expenses related to the sale of inventory balances, severance payments to employees, reimbursement of fines and penalties for contract termination, etc. These obligations may be conditioned by legal requirements or contractual terms or voluntarily assumed by the organization to individuals and legal entities whose interests will be affected due to discontinued operations.

Forecasting the costs of discontinued operations is relevant when developing a plan to restore the debtor's solvency in the course of financial rehabilitation or external management if this plan, among other things, provides for the sale of part of the debtor's property, closure of unprofitable production facilities, or re-profiling of production.

The duly estimated forthcoming expenses should be submitted to the arbitration court when deciding on the introduction of financial rehabilitation or to the creditors' meeting when approving the plan of external management.

By paragraph 8 of Accounting standards 16/02, "Information on discontinued operations" for obligations, "in respect of the amount or term of performance of which there is uncertainty, the organization recognizes by the established procedure estimated liability" [Ibid]. At the same time, practice should be guided by RAS 8/2010, "Estimated liabilities, contingent liabilities and contingent assets" [12].

Markedly, to create a valuation liability for discontinued operations, a detailed plan for "going out of business" must be developed, and all interested parties (dismissed employees, trade unions, counterparties, etc.) must be notified.

Potential costs associated with terminating business within the framework of bankruptcy procedures can be classified as estimated and contingent liabilities. The amount determines everything, including the probability of occurrence and the possibility of reliable assessment. We believe that the experience and professional judgment of the bankruptcy trustee have a certain influence: based on his experience in previous cases, he can determine the degree of liquidity of the assets to be sold and, consequently, the duration and cost of their realization.

In any case, information on discontinued operations should be reflected in the notes to the balance sheet and income statement and, in the case of a bankrupt company, in the bankruptcy trustee's report.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

There are perspectives on accounting for discontinued operations of an enterprise. Let us list a few key areas that can help improve accounting in this area:

- Development of unified standards. The creation and implementation of uniform international standards for accounting for discontinued operations can provide consistency and transparency in financial reporting, allowing for a more accurate reflection of enterprises' financial situations.
- Innovative technologies. The application of modern technologies such as blockchain and artificial intelligence can significantly improve the processes of recording and

analyzing data related to discontinued operations, increasing the accuracy and speed of information processing.

- Training and professional development. Increasing the knowledge and skills of accountants and CFOs in discontinued operations accounting can lead to better accounting and a better understanding of the legal and tax implications.
- Research and practical recommendations. Conducting research and developing practical guidance on accounting for discontinued operations can help businesses deal with this challenge more effectively and minimize negative consequences.
- Interdisciplinary approach. Specialists from various fields (economics, law, sociology) may be involved in analyzing the issues of accounting for discontinued operations, leading to a more comprehensive understanding of the problem and the development of practical solutions.
- Adaptation to changes in legislation. Continuously updating knowledge about legislative changes and their impact on accounting for discontinued operations will help enterprises adapt to new requirements in a timely manner.

Thus, given these directions, accounting for discontinued operations will likely become more efficient and transparent in the future, contributing to better financial reporting and risk management.

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